

Research Article

Withanolide A Ameliorates Global Cerebral Ischemia by Inhibiting Necroptosis Mediators PARP-1 and RIPK1

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Abstract: Cerebral ischemia is the second leading cause of global mortality and lacks proper therapeutics, which necessitates designing of novel strategies. Necroptotic pathway is involved in cerebral ischemic brain damage and designing multi target inhibitors against necroptotic pathway can be a suitable strategy to combat cerebral ischemic pathophysiological cascade. RIPK1 and PARP1 are established molecular mediators of necroptosis pathway and their inhibition might arrest the necroptotic pathway, thereby promoting cell survival. The present study investigates the ability of the phytochemical Withanolide A (WA) in inhibiting both PARP-1 and RIPK1 in-silico and in-vivo. In-silico molecular docking simulations show that WA inhibits both PARP-1 and RIPK1 with an affinity higher than PJ34 and Nec-1, the respective potent inhibitors. In-vivo studies in male Swiss albino mice were performed to evaluate the neuroprotective and necroptosis inhibiting ability of WA. WA shows an elaborate hydrophobic interaction pattern and greater number of hydrogen bond formation with both the enzymes in comparison to that of the reported inhibitors. In-vivo studies revealed that WA successfully reduces cerebral infarction percentage ($p < 0.001$) and significantly restores BBB disruption ($p < 0.001$). Treatment with WA also demonstrates down regulation of neuro-inflammatory cytokines TNF α ($p < 0.01$) and IL-1 β ($p < 0.05$) signifying inhibition of the necroptosis mediators by WA. WA treatment also enhances survival of brain cortical cells as evident from Annexin-FITC/PI staining. Hence, this study establishes WA as a potential dual target inhibitor of necroptosis pathway which can combat cerebral ischemia induced pathophysiology.

INTRODUCTION

Cerebral ischemia/reperfusion injury is known to cause irreversible brain damage due to loss of cerebral blood flow which eventually leads to activation of various inflammatory molecules further causing neuronal apoptosis (1). Recent studies have reported prevalence of a specially orchestrated pathway in cerebral ischemia induced cell death which exhibits characteristics of both apoptosis and necrosis (2) and has been termed as necroptosis (3). Necroptosis is reported to mediate neuronal death in ischemic brain (4) and RIP Kinase 1 (RIPK1) has been identified as its key molecular mediator (5). RIPK1 mediates necroptotic pathway by binding to complex I which is formed as a result of binding of TNF α to TNFR1 (6). RIPK1 also activates poly-ADP ribose polymerase 1 (PARP1) under oxidative stress condition (7), which is a common scenario in neurodegenerative disorders including cerebral ischemia. PARP-1 is another

known non-apoptotic death regulator plays an important role in caspase-independent neuronal death pathway (8). PARP1 causes translocation of apoptosis inducing factor (AIF) from mitochondria to nucleus (9) thereby causing DNA damage and in its attempt to repair DNA damage, PARP1 empties the ATP reservoir of cell, thereby causing membrane disruption and neuronal cell death (10). Inhibition of both RIPK1 and PARP1 by their respective inhibitors, Necrostatins and PJ34, respectively, has shown neuroprotection against ischemic conditions (11), which establishes these molecules as suitable therapeutic target for inhibitor designing in cerebral ischemia. But, till date, no known inhibitor has been reported that is capable of inhibiting both the molecules.

In the present study, efficacy of Withanolide A as a dual inhibitor of RIPK1 and PARP1 is evaluated. Withanolide A (WA) is a major constituent of root of Ayurvedic herb Aswagandha (*Withania somnifera*) (12). WA has been reported to confer therapeutic effect in

Alzheimer's disease (13), cause neurite regeneration (14)(15) and ameliorates stress in *C. elegans* (16). But, effect of WA on cerebral ischemia has not yet been studied. This study, for the first time evaluates neuroprotective efficacy of WA in global cerebral ischemia model of rat and also explores its ability as dual inhibitor of RIPK1 and PARP1.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Retrieval and preparation of enzymes

The 3-dimensional (3D) structures for PARP-1 and RIPK1 were downloaded from RCSB-PDB (PDB ID: 5DS3 and 4IT), respectively (17)(18) and energy minimized using UCSF-Chimera (19) after cleaning the molecules for heteroatoms (polyethylene glycol and sulfate ion for PARP1; ligand 1-HX and iodide for RIPK1). Steepest descent method for 100 steps (0.02 Å step size) and conjugate gradient method with ten steps of 0.02 Å step size each, was used for energy minimization of the molecules (20).

Ligand Preparation

Structure of WA was downloaded from PubChem database and that of PARP1 inhibitor PJ34 and RIPK1 inhibitor Necrostatin1 (Nec1) were downloaded from RCSB-PDB in .sdf format. PyRx-Python prescription 0.8 was used to convert the structures from .sdf to .pdb format and for their energy minimization by application of mmff94 force field and conjugate gradients optimization algorithm for 200 steps (21).

Molecular Docking Study

Molecular docking of PJ34, Nec-1 and WA with PARP1 and RIPK1 was performed using Auto Dock Tools 1.5.6 (22). The enzyme structures were assigned Gestgeiger partial charges after merging of non-polar hydrogen atoms and addition of polar hydrogen atoms, application of solvation parameters and Kollman charges. The Lamarckian genetic algorithm (LGA) was used to analyze active binding with different efficacy. The docking study for PARP1 and WA was performed by creating a grid box near the catalytic

domain amino acid residues with the number of points 90, 90 and 90, in X, Y and Z dimension and values for center of the grid box were assigned as 4.924, 36.5 and 9.798 for X, Y, and Z-center, respectively. For RIPK1, grid box with number of points 88,112 and 100 in the X, Y and Z direction respectively with center grid box value of 25.147, 2.253 and 54.305 for X, Y and Z-center, respectively for performing docking with WA. Grid box spacing for both the studies was kept at 0.375 Å ensuring that both the grid boxes entirely cover all the active site residues present at the binding site of the enzyme. For evaluating every docking interaction, 30 independent runs were performed with maximum number of 27,000 GA operations generated on a single population of 150 individuals (23). Interaction between enzymes were further visualized using UCSF-Chimera and LigPlot⁺ (v.1.4.5) (24).

Global Cerebral Ischemia Induction

Global cerebral ischemia was induced in anesthetized Swiss albino mice (weight 30 ± 2 gm) by ligating the bilateral common carotid arteries (CCAs) by aseptic non-absorbable silk sutures (3-0) after exposing the CCAs carefully with an incision along the vertical midline neck (25)(26). Anesthesia was induced in mice by intraperitoneal administration of combination of ketamine (50 mg/kg b.w.) and xylazine (10 mg/kg b.w.). Body temperature of the animals was maintained at 37±2°C during the surgical procedure. After 20 mins of occlusion, the ligature was excised cautiously using a sterile surgical blade and the incision was stitched followed by application of Povidone iodine. Reperfusion was allowed for 6 hrs after removal of the occlusion and the animals were returned to their cages at room temperature of 25±2°C with access to food and water. Sham group of animals were subjected to similar surgical procedures except CCA ligation. The workflow is described in Fig. 1. The protocols for performing animal experiments have been approved by Central Animal Ethical Committee at Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi (Registration No. 542/02/ab/CPCSEA).

Fig. 1: Schematic diagram for global ischemia induction

Administration of Withanolide A

Withanolide A was dispersed homogenously in phosphate buffer saline (PBS) by ultra-sonication and was administered i.p. to the animals of treated group after removal of occlusion. Dosage of administration was 50 mg/kg. Equal volume of PBS (without WA) was administered to the animals of vehicle group (16).

Cerebral Infarction Determination

Cerebral infarction in whole brain was determined by triphenyl tetrazolium chloride (TTC) staining in all three groups (i.e., sham, vehicle and treated; n=6 for each group) (27). The brains of the animals were carefully removed after 20 min occlusion and 6 hrs. reperfusion and washed in normal saline. 2mm thick coronal sections were cut after placing the brain on an ice pack and the tissue sections are incubated in 2% TTC solution at 37°C for 30 mins and further post-fixed in 10% formalin solution for 30 mins. The slices are scanned at 600 dpi and the images are quantified for percentage cerebral infarction using NIH ImageJ software (28).

Quantification of BBB disruption

Disruption of BBB as a result of ischemic insult was studied using Evan's Blue (EB) extravasation assay. In all three groups of animals (n=6), intravenous (i.v.) administration of EB was performed after 20 min occlusion and 6 hrs of reperfusion via the tail vein of mice (29). After 30 mins of EB administration, the animals were perfused with chilled saline solution via the left ventricle. The brains were

removed carefully after euthanizing the animals by cervical dislocation and washed in normal saline. Further, the brain was chopped into small pieces and incubated in formamide solution (8ml/1g dry tissue) for 48 hours at 56°C. The blue colored formamide solution was then collected in light protected microfuge tubes and used for quantification using multi-mode reader (BioTek Instruments, Inc., USA) at 620 nm. Concentration of EB in different samples were obtained from the standard curve prepared over the concentration range of 0.1- 12.8µg/mL.

Real Time qPCR Assay

Expression of TNF α and IL-1 β was studied to understand the ability of WA in inhibiting necroptosis. GAPDH was used as reference gene. Total mRNA was isolated from the brain tissues of animals of all three groups (n=4) using Trizol Reagent (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) according to manufacturer's protocol and reverse transcribed into cDNA using High-Capacity cDNA Reverse Transcription Kit (Applied Biosystems, Cat No.: 4368814) following manufacturer's instructions. The qualitative real time transcription was performed using Brilliant III Ultra-Fast QPCR Master Mix (Agilent Technologies, Cat No: 600882) using ABI 7900HT thermal cycler. Primer sequences used for the qPCR assay are listed in Table 1a (30). The parameters of thermal cycler for qPCR are stated in Table 1b. For all the samples, gene expression was quantified and analysed using $2^{-\Delta\Delta Ct}$ method and normalized with reference to GAPDH expression.

Table 1a: Primer sequences used for qPCR analysis

Gene Name	Primer Direction	Primer Sequence
GAPDH	Forward	5'GGTGAAGGTCGGTGTGAACG3'
	Reverse	5'CTCGCTCCTGGAAGATGGTG3'
TNF α	Forward	5'ATGCACCACCATCAAGGACTCAA3'
	Reverse	5'ACCACTCTCCCTTTCAGAACTC3'
IL-1 β	Forward	5'GCCCATCCTCTGTGACTCAT3'
	Reverse	5'AGGCCACAGGTATTTTGTGCG3'

Table 1b: Details for qPCR reaction

Cycle Name	Temperature	Time	Number of Cycles
Initial Denaturation	95°C	10 min	1
Final Denaturation	95°C	10 sec	40
Annealing	60°C	20 sec	1
Extension	72°C	20 sec	1
Termination	72°C	5 min	1

Table 2: Details of lowest energy confirmation of Enzyme-ligand interaction using AutoDock simulation

Enzyme	Inhibitor	Lowest Binding Energy (kcal/mol)	Estimated Inhibition Constant (K _i)	Amino acid residues participating in Hydrogen bond formation
PARP-1	PJ34	-8.45	637 nM	Gly 863
PARP-1	Withanolide A	-10.34	15.66 nM	Arg 878, Gly 863, Ala 880
RIPK1	Necrostatin1	-8.78	364.19 nM	Leu 78, Val 76
RIPK1	Withanolide A	-9.64	467.63 nM	Glu 142, Asn 99

Analysis of brain cell death

For analysing brain cell death, Annexin V-FITC and Propidium Iodide (PI) staining of freshly dissociated brain cells from animals of all three groups (n=4), was performed and observed under fluorescence microscope. Small sections of brain tissues were trypsinized at 37°C and centrifuged to obtain single cells which were further re-suspended in cold Hank's Balanced Salt solution (HBSS) for further staining procedure. Annexin V-FITC/PI staining was performed using Annexin V Kit: sc-4252 AK (Santa Cruz Biotechnology, USA) according to manufacturer's protocol (31).

RESULTS

Comparison of inhibition efficacy of WA and reported inhibitors

PJ34 and Nec-1 shows a binding energy of -8.45 kcal/mol and -8.78 kcal/mol while interacting with PARP-1 and RIPK1 respectively, whereas WA binds to PARP-1 and RIPK1 with binding energies -10.65 kcal/mol and -9.64 kcal/mol respectively. The value of binding energy of WA with both the enzymes is much lower than that of reported inhibitors, thus signifying a more stable interaction

between the enzymes and the ligand. The details of binding energy, estimated inhibition constant and hydrogen bond formation between WA, PJ34 and Nec-1 with PARP-1 and RIPK1 enzymes are listed in Table-2.

Analysis of binding patterns of ligands and the enzyme

Visualization with LigPlot+ revealed that PJ34 forms two hydrogen bonds with Gly 863 residue of PARP-1 whereas WA forms four hydrogen bonds with PARP-1 [Fig. 2a]. WA forms a single hydrogen bond Gly 863, two hydrogen bonds with Arg 878 and a single bond with Ala 880. Also, WA shows 13 hydrophobic interactions with PARP1, which greater than PJ34 which shows only 11 hydrophobic interactions [Fig. 2a, b]. WA forms two hydrogen bonds with amino acids Asn 99 and Glu 142 of RIPK1 [Fig 3a] and Nec-1 also shows two hydrogen bonds with Leu 78 and Val 76 [Fig. 3b]. But, interaction of Nec-1 and RIPK1 reveals only 7 hydrophobic interactions whereas WA shows hydrophobic interaction with 11 amino acid residues of RIPK1 [Fig. 3 a,b]. Visualization with UCSF Chimera also reveals that WA binds in catalytic groove of both PARP-1 and RIPK1 in a manner similar to PJ34 and Nec-1 [Fig. 2 and 3].

Fig. 2: [a] Interaction pattern of WA with PARP-1; UCSF- Chimera shows ribbon structure of PARP1 interacting with WA (ball and stick); surface interaction pattern showing binding of WA in the catalytic groove of PARP1 and visualization with LigPlot+ exhibits hydrogen bond and hydrophobic interactions. [b] Interaction pattern of PJ34 with PARP-1. Visualization with UCSF-Chimera shows PJ34 (ball and stick) interacting with PARP-1 ribbon structure. The surface structure shows that PJ34 binds in the catalytic groove of the enzyme. LigPlot+ results show formation of hydrogen bond of PJ34 with a single amino acid.

Fig. 3: UCSF-Chimera shows [a] WA and [b] Nec-1 (both shown in ball and stick) binds inside the catalytic groove of RIPK1. The surface structure shows that both the inhibitors bind in a similar manner inside the groove. LigPlot+ analysis shows hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic interaction of both the inhibitors with RIPK1.

WA post-treatment reduces cerebral infarction

TTC staining revealed white unstained brain regions (infarction) and red stained region (live brain tissue). Quantification with ImageJ software reveals a significant increase in cerebral infarction percentage in vehicle group animals as compared to that of sham group ($p < 0.001$). WA post treatment reduced the cerebral infarction percentage from 25.284% to 16.918% ($p < 0.001$) [Fig. 4].

WA post-treatment restores BBB disruption

WA post-treatment lowered leakage of EB in mice brain thereby signifying restoration of BBB. EB concentration in brains of Treated group animals was reduced by nearly 50% as compared to that of Vehicle group ($p < 0.001$) [Fig. 5].

WA post-treatment alleviates $TNF\alpha$ and $IL-1\beta$ expression

A significant increase in $TNF\alpha$ and $IL-1\beta$ expression in vehicle group animals was observed as compared to sham group ($p < 0.001$) indicating activation of necroptosis pathway. As compared to vehicle group animals, $TNF\alpha$ and $IL-1\beta$ expression is reduced in treated group ($p < 0.01$ and $p < 0.05$ respectively) [Fig. 6].

Brain cell death reduces due to WA post-treatment

Staining of cortical cells with Annexin-FITC and PI reveals increased number of FITC positive red cells and PI positive green cells in vehicle group as compared to sham group thus revealing features of apoptosis and necrosis. Less number of FITC positive and PI positive cells were observed in treated group animals [Fig. 7].

Fig. 4: WA treated group shows reduction of cerebral infarction as compared to vehicle group (***) signifies $p < 0.001$ between vehicle and treated; # signifies $p < 0.001$ between sham and vehicle).

Fig. 5: BBB disruption is observed in sham group as a result of cerebral ischemia induction (# signifies $p < 0.001$ between sham and vehicle group) whereas significant restoration of BBB is observed in Treated group (***) signifies $p < 0.001$).

Fig. 6: Global cerebral ischemia induces overexpression of $\text{TNF}\alpha$ and $\text{IL-1}\beta$ in vehicle group in comparison to sham group (# signifies $p < 0.001$). Expression of $\text{TNF}\alpha$ and $\text{IL-1}\beta$ is significantly down regulated in Treated group as compared to vehicle group (** signifies $p < 0.01$ and * signifies $p < 0.05$ between vehicle and treated group).

Fig. 7: Image of Apoptosis-FITC/PI-stained cells under fluorescence microscopy (40X). Cells in sham group appear less fluorescent whereas vehicle group cells are bright fluorescent red-green signifying apoptosis and necrosis. WA treatment group shows non-fluorescent cells. Number of cells in treated group are less as compared to vehicle group.

DISCUSSION

Necroptosis has been established as a prominent pathway involved in cerebral ischemia induced cell death (32). The enzyme RIPK1 has been identified as the principle mediator of this pathway and its inhibition by Nec-1 showed amelioration of ischemia induced pathophysiological damage in brain (33). Another molecule explicitly associated with this programmed necrotic cell death pathway is PARP1 (34). In condition of oxidative stress, RIPK1 activates PARP-1 (35) and both the

molecules orchestrates necroptotic cell death. Nec-1 and PJ34, respective inhibitors of RIPK1 and PARP1, has been reported to successfully combat necroptosis mediated liver injury and hepatitis (36), suggesting that inhibition of these two molecular mediators might be a possible strategy to combat necroptosis. The present study focuses on exploring the ability of WA, a primary constituent of *W. somnifera*, in combating necroptosis by dual inhibition of RIPK1 and PARP1.

In-silico studies reveal that WA binds to PARP-1 and RIPK1 with lower binding energy (-10.65 kcal/mol and -9.64 kcal/mol respectively) as compared to PJ34 (-8.45 kcal/mol) and Nec-1 (-8.78 kcal/mol) signifying a higher affinity of WA towards PARP1 and RIPK1 in comparison to their reported inhibitors. Comparison of binding pattern of WA and PJ34 with PARP1 revealed that, WA forms higher number of hydrogens bonds and shows greater number of hydrophobic interactions as compared to PJ34. PJ34 forms two hydrogen bonds with the amino acid Gly 863, a residue crucial for improving the protein-ligand interaction of PARP1 (37). WA forms a single hydrogen bond with Gly 863 but it also forms two hydrogen bonds with Arg 878, which is essential for stabilizing PARP1-ligand complex. WA also forms another hydrogen bond with Ala 880 and shows hydrophobic interaction with 13 other amino acids [Fig. 2]. In case of RIPK1, both WA and Nec-1 forms two hydrogen bonds with the amino acid residues of the catalytic domain of the enzyme. But WA shows higher number of hydrophobic interactions with RIPK1 in comparison to that of Nec-1. Overall, WA shows higher binding affinity towards both the enzymes and also reveals a more elaborate binding pattern with both PARP-1 and RIPK1 as compared to their inhibitors PJ34 and Nec-1, respectively. Thus, the *in-silico* study establishes WA as a potent inhibitor of both PARP-1 and RIPK1.

Further *in-vivo* evaluation of WA reveals that *i.p.* administration of WA (50mg/kg) reduces cerebral infarction by approximately 33.08% and EB extravasation assay shows that WA successfully restores BBB integrity, loss of which is a characteristic feature of cerebral ischemia (38). Restoration of BBB and reduction of cerebral infarction by WA indicates its neuroprotective ability in cerebral ischemic condition.

To understand whether neuroprotective ability of WA depends on its ability to inhibit necroptosis, expression of TNF α and IL-1 β was studied. Overexpression of TNF α and IL-1 β has been observed in RIPK1 mediated neuroinflammation (39). Overexpression of TNF α and IL-1 β is observed in vehicle group animals, which can be attributed to over-activation of RIPK1 and PARP1 in response to ischemic insult. WA administration significantly lowers expression of both TNF α ($p < 0.01$) and IL-1 β ($p < 0.05$) signifying down regulation of RIPK1 and PARP1. Also, Annexin-FITC/PI staining reveals that WA treatment lowers the number of necrotic and

apoptotic cells as compared to vehicle group. The cells were both Annexin-FITC and PI positive signifying damage of both cellular membrane and nuclear DNA [Fig. 6], which is suggestive of necroptosis. Presence of a smaller number of dead cells in treated group confirms the ability of WA in combating necroptosis mediated cell death.

CONCLUSION

The present study, for the first time, reveals the role of WA in combating necroptosis mediated cerebral ischemic damage. The *in-silico* findings suggestive of WA's ability in inhibiting PARP-1 and RIPK1 is confirmed by *in-vivo* study in mice model. The study showed that WA successfully reduces cerebral infarction, combats BBB disruption and reduces number of necroptotic cells, which confirm the neuroprotective ability of this phytochemical. WA also down regulates neuroinflammatory molecules TNF α and IL-1 β , which are overexpressed as a result of RIPK1 and PARP1 activation. Hence, it can be concluded that WA confers neuroprotection in global cerebral ischemia and can be a molecule of interest for future neurotherapeutics development.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors have declared that no conflict of interest exists.

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